

Enhancing the Application of Refractory Castables by Bridging Laboratory and Industrial Realities

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ABSTRACT

The global push for sustainability has marked the 21st century as an era of significant transformations across industries. In the steel industry, this change has accelerated the transition from bricks to castables, a class of materials offering distinct advantages, such as the ability to achieve their final shape during application, the absence of expansion joints and shorter installation times. Castables also provide sustainability benefits, including improved energy efficiency, extended service life and increased use of recycled and sustainable materials. However, these advantages come with challenges, particularly during the pre-heating stage. Phase transformations, coupled thermal and mass transport phenomena, pressurized steam release (and explosive spalling risks), and numerous microstructural changes during drying make this stage one of the most complex to understand, control and ensure safety. Consequently, achieving effective drying of castables is a multifaceted task that requires addressing various criteria. Traditional approaches and laboratory studies often are based on qualitative techniques or small-scale samples and frequently fail to replicate and manage the phenomena encountered on an industrial scale. In this context, emerging technologies, such as the integration of wireless sensors with computational models, hold significant potential to digitize and efficiently manage drying processes within steel plants. This study investigates pressure and temperature distributions within castables during drying using a modified experimental setup comprising a high-capacity furnace and sensors for real-time monitoring. The setup replicates some conditions in steel ladles by unilaterally heating a block, enabling the formation of temperature and pressure gradients while simultaneously measuring these parameters at various positions. The experimental results supported the calibration of advanced numerical models capable of simulating temperature and pressure distributions within the material. This innovative combination of sensors and modeling bridges the gap between laboratory research and industrial conditions, offering a pathway for adaptation to industrial equipment.

INTRODUCTION

The global drive toward reducing CO₂ emissions and promoting circular economy principles is reshaping industrial practices, particularly in energy and material intensive sectors such as steelmaking. This transition involves the adoption of more sustainable production routes, including hydrogen-based reduction and increased scrap utilization, which in turn require significant adaptations throughout the steel production chain¹.

One notable shift is the growing reliance on Electric Arc Furnace (EAF)-based refining processes¹. Although advantageous in terms of energy efficiency and raw material flexibility, these routes also introduce new challenges, particularly in the form of more intensive secondary refining stages to meet strict compositional standards. Among these,

more demanding on the refractory linings and leading to shorter service-lives and more frequent relinings.

Monolithic refractories, especially castables, are increasingly favored for their sustainability benefits, lower labor requirements, and faster installation. However, the in-situ processing of castables presents its own set of challenges, especially during the drying and pre-heating stages, which must be handled with care. The drying stage, in particular, stands out as the most energy-intensive, time-consuming and risky phase of the relining process².

During the initial heat-up, both free and chemically bonded water within the castable evaporate, generating pressurized vapor inside the material's porous structure². This internal pressure, combined with thermal gradients, can lead to explosive spalling², a violent phenomenon that can severely damage the refractory lining, compromising nearby equipment and posing serious risks to personnel.

In industrial practice, specific features of the applied drying curves, namely temperature plateaus and low heating rates, are the primary strategy to control the temperature and pressure evolution during this critical phase. Yet, due to the inherent complexity of the process and the gap between laboratory analysis and on-site conditions, these curves are often based on overly conservative heat-up schedules. As a result, drying times become excessively long while the risk of explosive spalling is not fully mitigated².

A key challenge in improving the accuracy of numerical models that simulate drying behavior lies in determining reliable, temperature-dependent material properties, particularly permeability³. T. Cunha et al.⁴ demonstrated the importance of incorporating temperature-dependent permeability in thermo-hydraulic models, showing that such models predict significantly different internal pressures compared to models using constant permeability values. This aspect is particularly relevant in castables formulations containing polymeric fibers, whose permeability behavior is highly sensitive to temperature⁵. As the temperature rises, phenomena such as fiber's dissolution, swelling, melting and decomposition⁶, along with associated phase and microstructural changes, introduce considerable uncertainty into permeability measurements and modeling efforts.

To address these limitations, this study investigates the potential of combining experimental data from customized high-temperature tests with advanced numerical models. By replicating industrial-like thermal boundary conditions and applying inverse problem-solving methodologies, the aim is to bridge the gap between laboratory-scale insights and real-world application, ultimately contributing to the development of a computational tool to achieve safer and more efficient refractory castable drying process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Refractory Castable

The refractory material investigated in this study is a commercially available high-alumina castable containing in-

calcium aluminate cement (CAC). To improve drying behavior and reduce pressurization risks during initial heating, polymeric fibers are added as drying agents. They enhance pore connectivity, allowing safer vapor release and lowering the risk of explosive spalling⁶.

Modified Experimental Set-Up

A laboratory furnace was adapted in this study to better accommodate a representative castable sample under partially industrial-like thermal constraints.

Insulating refractory bricks were installed around the lateral surfaces of the sample to ensure effective thermal insulation. This configuration restricted lateral heat losses and promoted a predominantly unidirectional heat flow across the specimen. The castable samples had dimensions of $130 \times 114 \times 100$ mm, with the heat flux directed along the longest dimension (130 mm).

Wireless sensors were embedded at fixed positions in the mold to monitor both temperature and vapor pressure during the test. Temperature sensors were embedded at four distinct depths: 0 mm (Hot Face), 30 mm, 60 mm, and 130 mm (Cold Face). In addition, a single pressure sensor was positioned at the 30 mm depth. The data was later used for the calibration of the numerical models. Figure 1 illustrates the test sample used in the setup, including the positioning of the embedded sensors.

Fig. 1: Representation of the sample produced.

The test procedure involved preheating the furnace to 600 °C. Once this temperature was reached, the castable sample, along with the insulating system, was placed in front of the furnace.

Fig. 2: Technical drawing of equipment, showing both an external view (a) and a cross-sectional view (b).

Numerical Model

The modeling strategy adopted in this work involved two complementary stages. In the first stage, a purely thermal simulation was conducted using commercial finite element ANSYS[®] software. This initial model served as a preliminary tool for fine tuning the thermal response of the system. It enabled the estimation of heat transfer coefficients and the refinement of other boundary conditions to be later used in a more comprehensive analysis.

In the second stage, a coupled thermo-hydraulic model was implemented based on the approach developed by Moreira et al.³. This model, built using open-source tools, primarily Python and the FEniCS finite element framework, employs a single-phase formulation to describe heat and mass transport within a porous medium saturated with water. The governing equations include conservation laws for mass and energy (equations 1 and 3), along with Neumann boundary conditions (equations 2 and 4), and are solved using the Finite Element Method (FEM).

Mass balance:

$$ResP = \frac{\partial w(P_v, T, P_{vn}, T_{vn})}{\partial t} v_1 dx + \left(\frac{\alpha(P_{vn}, T_{vn})}{g} \right) \nabla P_v * \nabla v_1 dx - \frac{\partial w_d(T, T_n)}{\partial t} v_1 dx \quad (1)$$

$$ResP = h_m(P_v - P_{v\infty})v_1(ds(1) + ds(2) + ds(3)) \quad (2)$$

Energy balance:

$$ResT = \rho_s(T_n)C_p(T_n)\frac{dT}{dt}v_2 dx + \lambda(T)(\nabla T * \nabla v_2)dx - C_a(T_n) * \frac{\partial w(P_v, T, P_{vn}, T_{vn})}{\partial t}v_2 dx + C_{pl}(T_n) * \left(\frac{\alpha(P_{vn}, T_{vn})}{g} \right) \nabla P_{vn} * \nabla T_n v_2 dx \quad (3)$$

$$ResT = h_{hot}(T, T_{furnace}, t) * (T - T_{furnace})v_2 ds(1) + h_{cold}(T) * (T - T_{room})v_2 ds(2) \quad (4)$$

The model simultaneously computes pressure and temperature curves as primary outputs, while also estimating the evolving water content as a secondary output. Its implementation requires the definition of spatial and temporal discretizations, material properties, initial and boundary conditions, and post-processing routines.

Inverse Problem Methodology

Among recent efforts to improve the calibration of thermo-hydraulic models, Valentin et al.⁷ proposed a strategy aimed at accurately reproducing the pressure behavior of refractory castables. In their study, a trial-and-error method was employed to identify both the hydral capacity function $(\partial W(P_v, T, P_{vn}, T_{vn}))/\partial t$ and the material's permeability⁷.

Fig. 3: Pressure at different depths for simulation and experiment. Adapted from 7.

Based on the results, exemplified in Figure 3, the authors reported a lack of robustness in the trial-and-error methodology, particularly when applied to interdependent variables. As a result, they highlighted the need for more systematic approaches for the reliable identification of such parameters⁷.

In this context, the present work implements a combination of empirical measurement of the hydral capacity function, as defined by Bazant et al.⁸, with a mathematically grounded calibration method based on optimization algorithms. Specifically, an Inverse Problem Methodology is applied to identify a correction parameter associated with permeability. This approach is especially important in materials where direct measurement is difficult due to temperature-dependent effects and structural changes.

This methodology, implemented using the Nelder–Mead optimization algorithm, systematically adjusts a target parameter “x” (a correction factor linked to the material's permeability) to minimize the discrepancy between simulated and experimentally measured pressure curves. It is worth noting that, in practice, the calibrated “x” may also compensate for modeling uncertainties or simplifications and therefore acts more as a corrective coefficient than a direct physical property.

The procedure involves iteratively modifying an initial guess for “x,” running the thermo-hydraulic simulation and computing the error between the predicted and measured pressure profiles. The process is repeated until convergence is achieved i.e., up to the simulated results closely reproduce the experimental data.

Despite its limitations, this methodology provides a systematic and robust framework for enhancing the predictive accuracy of thermo-hydraulic models and ultimately contributes to the optimization of industrial drying schedules and the improvement of safety and efficiency in refractory castable applications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental test used for numerical model calibration followed the procedure detailed in the Materials and Methods section. Figures 4 and 5 show the results obtained from this test.

Fig. 4: Experimental temperature results, applied on thermal model calibration.

Fig. 5: Experimental pressure and temperature results at 30mm depth, applied on thermo-hygro model calibration.

Table I and Figure 6 summarize the relevant material properties measured for this study. These include specific density (ρ_s), specific heat capacity (C_p), initial cement concentration (W_c), initial water content (W_0), dehydration water (W_d) and thermal conductivity (λ), which are fundamental to both thermal and coupled hygrothermal modeling.

Tab. I: The properties required by the thermo-hygro and thermal models.

Properties	Range
ρ_s [kg/m ³]	2500 - 3000
C_p [J/(kg·K)]	750 - 1000
W_c [kg/m ³]	240 - 330
W_0 [kg/m ³]	95 - 125

Fig. 6: Experimental data and the fitted curve for thermal conductivity (a); and dewatering behavior along with its derivative on temperature (b).

The experimental dataset also enabled a detailed assessment of the thermal boundary conditions, which were incorporated into a commercial ANSYS[®] thermal model. Following the relations proposed by Santos et al.⁹, a series of simulations were conducted to derive the heat transfer coefficients (HTCs) on both the cold and hot faces of the sample during the drying test. These analyses also enabled the evaluation of potential heat losses through the lateral surfaces. However, the results confirmed the insulating performance of the refractory bricks, indicating negligible lateral heat transfer. This step proved crucial for bridging the experimental and numerical results and provided a solid foundation for the subsequent development of the coupled hygro-thermal model. The computed HTCs are illustrated in Figure 7.

Fig. 7: Heat transfer coefficients obtained via ANSYS[®] analyses.

Figure 8 compares the results obtained using a constant permeability value, Figure 8 (a), with those from the Inverse Problem Method (IPM), which accounts for temperature-dependent permeability, Figure 8 (b). In the first case, Figure 8 (a), significant discrepancies are observed: the peak pressure is shifted in time and the overall shape of the curve deviates from experimental results. For instance, the simulated pressures after approximately 0.5 hours are consistently higher than those measured experimentally, indicating that the assumed permeability values are underestimated in that temperature range.

In contrast, the model calibrated via IPM, Figure 8 (b), provides a better fit across the entire pressure curve, capturing both the magnitude and the timing of pressure development.

Fig. 8: Pressure curve comparison using constant permeability (a) and after IPM calibration (b).

Assuming a single, constant value for key properties introduces significant uncertainty into the model, particularly in its ability to capture the complex microstructural, chemical, and physical changes that take place during heating. This simplification often results in noticeable deviations, including shifts in the peak pressure, inaccurate amplitude predictions, and changes in curve morphology.

By applying the IPM, the model is able to closely replicate experimental pressure profiles, effectively incorporating, or compensating for the complex underlying phenomena.

Figure 9 summarizes the results obtained, showing the comparison of the simulated and measured temperature and pressure for the desired depths. The good agreement between the results highlights the capability of the proposed methodology. These results represent a crucial first step toward the development of a comprehensive computational tool aimed at improving the understanding of castable drying behavior.

Fig. 9: Thermohygro model results after calibration.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The main objective of this study was to initiate the development of a computational tool to enhance the understanding, safety and efficiency of the drying process in refractory castables in industrial scenarios. To achieve this, a hybrid approach combining experimental data and numerical modeling was employed. Additionally, the study aimed to advance the indirect estimation of material properties that are challenging to be measured directly, by proposing mathematically grounded methodologies which are more robust than previously applied strategies such as trial-and-error.

A key achievement of this work was the successful calibration of a thermo-hydraulic numerical model using experimental data obtained under partially industrial thermal boundary conditions. This strategy bridges the often-observed gap between laboratory-scale research and on-site industrial

application, ensuring that the resulting models are both theoretically sound and practically relevant.

The use of inverse problem-solving methodologies, particularly the implementation of the Nelder–Mead optimization algorithm, proved to be a promising approach for calibrating numerical models. It enabled the indirect estimation of a correction parameter associated with permeability — a property known for its strong temperature dependence and measurement complexity. The results demonstrated the sensitivity of pressure development to permeability variations and emphasized the need to adopt temperature-dependent values to ensure accurate simulation. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that further validation steps are required to verify the reliability of the calibration procedure and the model's predictive capabilities under different experimental conditions.

The work carried out at Tata Steel focused on investigating the drying behavior of refractory castables under conditions that more closely replicate industrial environments. By integrating wireless sensors with numerical modeling techniques, this study has demonstrated the potential of hybrid experimental–computational approaches to deepen the understanding of the complex thermo-hydraulic phenomena occurring during the critical drying stage of castable refractories.

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